

**SOCIO-SCIENTIFIC ISSUE BASED INSTRUCTION:
AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH OF CURRICULUM
TRANSACTION IN SCIENCE**

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Abstract

Growing emphasis on situated learning in science and shift in prime vision of scientific literacy from development of scientific attitude to development of citizenship has created the need of incorporation of socio-scientific issues for transaction of science curriculum. The present paper attempted to conceptualize the need of socio-scientific issue based instruction in science education as well as the epistemological framework and expertise required for such teaching. It explained the controversial nature and its social relevance which make these issues an effective tool for situated learning and developing scientific literacy for citizenship. It also depicted that how Socio-scientific issue based instruction does help learners exploring the controversy around the issue logically and developing deep insight into the scientific concepts involved through recognition of the category of reasonable disagreements among learners and the necessary dispositions and modes of experiences for these disagreements during discussion on the part of the teacher.

Key Words: Socio-Scientific Issues, Situated Learning, Scientific Literacy for Citizenship, Socio-Scientific Issue based Instruction

Introduction

There is a budding impetus in teaching science on teaching scientific content in relation to socially relevant life situations (Gilbert, 2006) and socio-scientific issues provide a useful means to situated learning. These issues offer perspectives and frames what is relevant to learn as well as the context or situation in relation to which scientific concepts and principles are defined meaningfully (Sadler, 2009). Socio-scientific issues based instruction combines the use of controversial socially relevant real world issues with course content to engage students in their learning and supplies both motivation and ownership of learning to the learner. Socio-scientific issues

involve the deliberate use of scientific topics that require students to engage in dialogue, discussion and debate. They are usually controversial in nature but have added element of moral reasoning or the evaluation of ethical concerns in the process of arriving at decisions regarding possible resolutions of those issues. The intent is that such issues are personally meaningful and engaging students, require the use of evidence-based reasoning, and provide a context for understanding scientific information. (Latourelle, 2010; Zeidler & Nicols, 2009).

Characteristics of Socio-Scientific Issues

Socio-scientific issues have procedural and conceptual connections to the sciences and are viewed socially significant (Sadler, 2004). These are controversial, socially relevant real world problems that are informed by science and often include an ethical component. These are usually value laden and the juxtaposition of science and ethics can be uncomfortable for scientists, teachers and students who define science in terms of objectivity (Sadler et al., 2006). Bridges (1986) has suggested that controversial issues are those reasonable disagreements that incorporate moral and social values but it would be problematic to decide to what extent there was a value laden element in any disagreement. Some basic characteristics of socio-scientific issues are-

- Are they socially relevant
- Controversial, having no fixed or universally held point of view (Crick, 1998)
- Are they real rather than fabricated
- Data supported or evidence based (Latourelle, 2009; Zeidler & Nicols, 2009)
- Informed by science and ethical, legal and social components involved
- Illustrating the nature and process of sciences
- Constituted of questions which are philosophical as well as empirical in nature- socially constructed existing at the intersection of differing human interests, values and motivations (Robottom, 2012).

- Reasonable disagreement among authentic groups in the society

Socio-Scientific Issues as Contexts for Situated Learning

Socio-scientific issues provide social contexts which inform both the selection and the situational framing of the content to be taught, because the authentic context supports the specification of a concept's meaning and coherence of concepts within a larger whole (Herrington & Herrington, 2006, Van Oers, 1998). These issues generally belong to social practices incorporating scientific principles and concepts and have ethical, legal and social aspects for the professional participants as well as clients involved for making reasonable decisions on them (Gearon, 2003). Thus, these provide personally meaningful context giving relevance to what is learned and in doing so to promote students' motivation (Sadler, 2009).

Socio-Scientific Issues as Tools for Realizing the Goal of Science Education as Science for All or Scientific Literacy for Citizenship

In the present context the goal of science education has shifted from development of scientific temper or scientific competency to understanding of the situations where scientific principles and concepts are applied. Socio-scientific issues serve as tools to conceptualize the goal of science education for all by providing students with opportunity for argument or dialogue on these issues based on some evidences as well as moral reasoning. As a result, in any practice or issue of individual as well as social concern employing scientific concepts decision can be made at a larger scale involving people from different sectors of society that such practices should be carried on or discontinued. Thus, these issues prepare the students who will be the immediate practitioners or clients in these practices for a kind of moral citizenship analyzing ethical, social and legal consequences of their decision making process in these situations (Kolsto, 2001; Levinson, 2006; Sadler, 2004).

Socio-Scientific Issues Based Teaching Approach

Socio-scientific issue based instruction is similar in its teaching approach to case based and problem based teaching in that they both

frame science content within a social context or a story but in this approach the students will not be able to solve the issue but they will develop a position based on their investigation as they explore the controversy around the issue whereas in case based or problem based learning the students are asked to find an answer or solution of the problem under consideration (Klosterman & Sadler; 2010). In socio-scientific issue based teaching approach the learners collaborate with a group that represents authentic groups in society. They acquire conceptual understanding and apply it in making and evaluating personal, societal and global decisions on these issues. This approach also incorporates evidence based learning as the learners require explaining phenomena backed by some evidence and thus help in authentic assessments of students' learning (Wilmes & Howarth, 2009). They start with the real world problem and identify the issues and the available disciplines involved (contextualization) then these disciplines are integrated with scientific concepts of the discipline to be taught (de-contextualization) and after developing the conceptual understanding, it is applied to address the problem (re-contextualization).

Epistemological Framework for Teaching Socio-Scientific Issues

Levinson (2006) proposed an epistemological framework for socio-scientific issue based instruction dependent on three strands - i) categories of reasonable disagreement ii) the dispositions necessary to engage in reasonable disagreement iii) the modes of thought and experience which can best illuminate those disagreements. The reasonable disagreement involves an account of the sources or causes of disagreement between reasonable persons (Rawls, 1993) and the categories of disagreement between authentic groups in society on socio-scientific issues is informed by nature, availability, adequacy and relevance of evidences involved (Levinson, 2006). These categories reflect whether people are attached to the same or different values; differences in priorities about the same values or differences in interpretations about an issue (Bridge, 1986). Communicative virtues are those dispositions necessary to attempt dialogue across differences among learners. These are a cluster of intellectual and affective dispositions that together promote open, inclusive and undistorted communication (Rice & Burbles, 1992).

Hence, based on the context of discussion communicative virtues should be involved. There are two ways of structuring experiences to explicate reasonable disagreement. First is logico-scientific mode which is linked to the role of evidence. It deals in general causes and their empirical establishments through some evidences or tests. The other is narrative mode which provides a means of interpretations allowing people to relate and listen to tell of experiences not yet known, understood or imagined by other parties. Thus, while dealing with controversial socio-scientific issues in order to arrive at a collective decision appropriate criteria should be established, learners should work collaboratively keeping in consideration evidences available as well as their limitations and listening and relating to what each other has to say.

Expertise Required For Teaching Science in the Context of Socio-Scientific Issues

The expertise required for socio-scientific issue based instruction can be grouped into subject matter expertise, pedagogical expertise, interpersonal expertise and moral expertise.

Subject Matter Expertise

From a situated learning perspective subject matter expertise not only deals with subject content but also the authentic practices involving socio-scientific issues. These comprise of knowledge of relevant parts of the curriculum as well as the current practices which have conceptual and procedural relationship with these scientific contents. Many studies have stressed context based expertise for teaching science concepts in the context of socio-scientific issues (Levinson, 2006; Levinson & Turner, 2001; Zeidler et al., 2005). The context bound knowledge demands for several extracurricular scientific concepts to align the science curriculum with developments in the authentic practices (Boerwinkel, Verhoelff & Waarlo, 2008) which help students understanding the characteristics of socio-scientific issues as uncertain, complex, moral and based on probability which in turn contribute to understand successful decision making in these issues (Van der Zande et al., 2011). The content transcending topics dealing with science dimension of socio-scientific issues like science as a social process, limitations of science and values in science and critical attitude also

provide knowledge base for teaching science in the context of socio-scientific issues by offering knowledge about science i.e. the situations and practices where scientific principles are used (Kolsto, 2001). The content transcending topics along with extracurricular concepts provide an overview of ethical, legal and social aspects of socio-scientific issues which in turn stressed the importance of students' ability in moral reasoning and consequently of teachers' knowledge of moral reasoning (Van der Zande et al., 2011). Thus, the subject matter expertise for socio-scientific issue based instruction encompasses knowledge of relevant curricular concepts, extracurricular concepts, content transcending topics, characteristics of socio-scientific issues and its legal, ethical and social aspects as well as students' ability in moral reasoning.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge Expertise

Lewis & Kattmann (2004) stressed on a process-oriented approach starting from the context of a visible phenomenon for situated learning. Rational dialogue and argumentation seem to be an effective teaching-learning activity to bring in learners' different perspectives in the controversial socio-scientific issues and to strengthen learners' moral reasoning on these issues (Levinson, 2006; Van der Zande et al., 2012). With respect to problem or case based learning approach of socio-scientific issue based learning the students should be stimulated to construct their own conceptual understanding of a given problem or socio-scientific issue and students' self regulation of their learning processes (Boersma et al., 2007; Van der Zande et al., 2012). Narrative methods should be used for starting the lesson to stimulate learners change their perspective and provoke their moral empathy towards the clients and future children who would be the victim of the practices involving socio-scientific issues (Van der Zande et al., 2012). During dialogue and argumentation on scientific issues the teacher should seek to recognize the category of disagreement based on the role of evidence and social dimensions and the necessary pre-supposed dispositions for reasonable disagreement to create congenial environment for discussion as well as the mode of thought involved (Levinson, 2006) so that the learner can explore the phenomenon in a systematic and logical manner.

Interpersonal Expertise

A good interrelationship between teacher and students is a precondition for socio-scientific issue based instruction. Based on the model for interpersonal teacher behavior tolerant/ authoritative profile is best suited for maintaining a structure that supports an environment appropriate for rational argumentation on socio-scientific issues. Tolerant authoritative teachers support student responsibility and freedom. They use a variety of methods to which students respond well. There is very little need to enforce rules. They frequently organise their lessons around small group work. While the classroom environment resembles the authoritative class but there exists closer relationships with students. This environment stimulates learners for moral reflection (Van der Zande et al., 2012).

Moral Expertise

During discussion or dialogue the teachers should not try to impose their own values on students rather the students should be promoted to explore their own values. They should take the stance of value development and value communication by choosing a role of absent leader or committed instructor (Van der Zande et al., 2012).

Conclusion

Due to its ability to illustrate nature and processes of science and its social relevance socio-scientific issues are used to provide meaningful context to transact scientific concepts effectively. Besides providing context for situational learning, its controversial nature facilitate learners for moral reasoning on these issues and thus prepare them for decision making in the practices involving these issues as future practitioners or clients. Because of the support provided by socio-scientific issues for situational learning and scientific literacy for citizenship socio-scientific issue based instruction is being incorporated as an innovative approach for transaction of curriculum in science education. This approach involves collaboration among learners in small groups and representing authentic groups in society having different perspectives on socio-scientific issues. Like problem based or case based learning, it frames science content within a social context but instead of reaching a final answer to the problem, the students

develop a position to make a logical decision on the problem or issue.

Teaching science situated in the context of socio-scientific issues demands certain expertise on the art of science teacher. Subject matter expertise comprise of knowledge of subject content, extracurricular concepts to align the science curriculum with developments in the authentic practices, content transcending topics, characteristics of socio-scientific issues and students' ability of moral reasoning. Regarding pedagogical content knowledge expertise the teacher should adopt an evidence based process oriented approach where the learners have self regulation of their learning process. The methods like dialogue, argumentation, discussion, role play are considered to be the most appropriate for socio-scientific issue based teaching. For creating conducive environment for discussion the teacher should adopt an authoritative/ tolerant interpersonal behaviour. Regarding moral expertise, the learners should be allowed for moral reflection on legal, social and ethical aspects of socio-scientific issues through value development and value communication.

Moreover, to ensure effective discussion on socio-scientific issues categories of reasonable disagreements among the groups of learners, necessary communicative virtues for discussion and the modes of thought and experiences revealing these disagreements should be recognized at the earliest.

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